

DIFFERENT VIEWS ABOUT PERSON-ORIENTED EDUCATION AND CITIZEN UPBRINGING

Babayev J.*The chief of the chair "English and methods"
Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

Along with national values related to the opportunities for civic education of personality-oriented education, there are also universal values. Therefore, in terms of universal values, we considered it expedient to conduct an analysis of the opportunities for civic education of person-oriented education. To this end, we have reviewed a number of sources from the recent past. The article elaborates different views about person-oriented education and citizen upbringing. Y.A. Comenius, Thomas Jefferson, Benjamin Franklin, George Washington, John Locke and others had very valuable pedagogical views about person-oriented education and citizen upbringing. Some of them took life examples about themselves and included them in the memories which can be found in textbooks or manuals.

Keywords: upbringing, citizen, personality-oriented, education, universal values.

As it is known, starting from the second half of XIX century, many Azerbaijani intellectuals considered it more expedient to refer to the provisions put forward in the works of European and Russian pedagogues in order to form the personality of the new era, and thus these sources became a source for our pedagogical thought. For the same reason, in order to study the scientific and theoretical basis of the ideas related to the problem we studied, we turned to the works of famous American, European and Russian teachers. Aesthetic values bestow happiness and pleasure to a person with various types of beauties while moral values form the children's physical habits and mental attitudes [1].

N.K. Goncharov's book "Basic pedagogy" states that for the first time Y.A. Comenius (1592-1670) explained the issues of training, upbringing and education on a scientific basis and initiated them. For example, he explained the essence and content of pedagogical phenomena on the basis of the principle of nature, and said that knowledge should be deeply and firmly imparted to students, because in nature, trees whose roots are deep in the soil are strong. Explaining issues of training and education in accordance with natural phenomena is simple and inaccurate compared to modernity. However, these ideas were a complete novelty for their time, a turning point in the development of pedagogical thought.

Comenius's didactic rules were based on the development of personal activity. Y.A. Comenius said that without accurate, meaningful knowledge of objects, events and their interactions in the environment, there can be no clear, logical and truly rich speech. Such is the sequence of Comenius's didactics – from visual observation to comprehension, from comprehension to memorization and from speech to expression, exercises and practical activity. Comenius highly valued the role of the teacher in the organization of the educational process at school. According to Y.A. Comenius, the task of a teacher is to encourage children to learn with their beautiful examples. A teacher must master the art of teaching and be a master of his craft. Comenius compares the teacher to an active sculptor, an educator, or the sun that illuminates everything [2, p.58]. Comenius was an optimistic educator. He had

great faith in man, in his power, in his beautiful inclinations and desires. In his book *The Great Didactics*, he said, "Everyone was born for a basic purpose, to be human." "In order for a person to be a real person, he must be educated" [4,p.36]. Comenius aims to form each student as a person. Comenius, who created the world's first school experience, even valued the personality-oriented nature of religious education. He considered it expedient to teach children the basics of exact sciences, natural sciences and social sciences in the classroom system, while creating the classroom system, i.e. laying the foundation of secular education. Against the background of teaching the basics of knowledge, he advised the development of students' physical abilities, the formation of their artistic tastes, and the organization of leisure time to provide them with interesting information about natural and social phenomena. Comenius's recommendations and advice can be considered the first initiative for a person-centered approach. Thus, as early as the seventeenth century, Jan Amos Comenius in his works showed the first elements of a personality-oriented approach and civic education.

The promotion of progressive pedagogical ideas in North America is associated with the names of Thomas Jefferson (1743-1826), George Washington (1732-1799) and Benjamin Franklin (1706-1790).

Thomas Jefferson, a prominent American educator, the third president of the United States, and the main author of the Declaration of Independence, affirmed that an illiterate nation could not think of freedom. At the initiative of Thomas Jefferson, a three-tier comprehensive school model was developed in American schools. This model was the first attempt to move away from the European education system, which was rooted in American schools at the time.

George Washington's idea that "knowledge is the surest foundation of prosperity in any country" played an important role in the development of education in eighteenth-century America.

Benjamin Franklin, a prominent scientist, public figure, and one of the unique figures of the American Enlightenment, lived a meaningful life of 84 years. When you look at his life, it is clear that throughout his career he went through the stages of self-motivation, self-upbringing, self-education. These stages can be

considered as one of the examples of education for the development and formation of personality. In order to get acquainted with such examples of upbringing, it is necessary to pay more attention to the way of life of B. Franklin on the stages of self-education, self-upbringing, self-motivation and self-esteem. Franklin was born in 1706 into a Boston artisan family. He studied grammar school for only two years and dropped out of school to help his father. At the age of thirteen, Franklin began working as an assistant in his brother's printing press, and later persevered in his education, making great strides in the natural sciences, philosophy, economics, and literature. Franklin's scientific achievements were recognized by the whole world, and he was elected an honorary member of several academies, including the Russian Academy of Sciences. As an economist, Franklin defined the theory of value in 1729, half a century before A. Smith. His philosophical views were formed under the influence of such enlighteners as Locke, Sheftsbury, Priestley, Collins, and to some extent moved away from radical deism. It should be noted that Franklin has always expressed his deist views with caution in his own way. He sought to enlighten his countrymen by publishing secular and bourgeois newspapers. Like all American educators, he took an active part in revolutionary movements and was a member of the commission that edited the Declaration of Independence. Named the "first great American", Franklin was sent to Europe, where he signed agreements with a number of European countries and succeeded in sending a French navy to America. Some French officers and young people from different European countries voluntarily went to America to help in the war of liberation, while the French capitalists supplied the revolutionary army with military ammunition. In 1728, on his initiative, the "Philosophical-Enlightenment Society" was established in Philadelphia. Important issues of morality, politics and education were discussed at the meetings of the society. Franklin proposed a pedagogical concept for the reorganization of school education. He criticized the scholastic system of education, demanding that students first learn scientific knowledge, not religion. The Academy and General Education School were opened in 1751 in Philadelphia under Franklin's project. The secondary school consisted of three departments (Latin, English grammar school, mathematics). Students were independent in choosing the type of school. These schools were designed for both boys and girls. These types of schools spread rapidly in America [3, p.33].

As a writer, Franklin was influenced by English journalists R. Steele, J. Addison (1711-1714). Didactics had a special place in his work. The author's didactic views, along with other works, found their bright expression in the most famous and large-scale work "Biography", which was published after his death. The Biography also writes about Franklin's code of ethics: "I came up with a very bold and difficult plan to achieve moral perfection. I wanted to live without making mistakes, to overcome my natural desires, my habits and everything that society pushed me to do. So I knew what was good and what was bad, and I wondered why

I should always follow one and avoid the other. However, I soon realized that this issue was more complicated than I had anticipated: "But soon found I had undertaken a task of more difficulty than I had imagined" [5, p. 51].

Usually, children, adolescents and young people are formed in the family, at school with the help of education and acquire the spiritual wealth of mankind in this way. The process of upbringing creates the basis for the emergence of the function of self-education. In this case, we can say that the socially important goals of education are not only perceived by the trainee, but also accepted. Adolescents and young people who want to improve themselves can achieve great success in life if they try to follow organized educational activities. The positive manifestation of the function of self-education can also be seen in the formation of the prominent American public figure Benjamin Franklin as a scientist, personality and educator. He wrote: "My father admonished me when I was a child and often repeated the words of the prophet Solomon: 'If a man is diligent in his work, he will be able to stand before the king, and he will not stand before ordinary people.' From then on, I realized that the only way to get rich and different was to work hard, but I wondered if I could really stand up to kings. As a result, I stood before five kings and was honored to have dinner with the King of Denmark" [5, p. 49].

B. Franklin writes about his family: "We have an English proverb: He that would thrive, Must ask his wife. This proverb can be interpreted as follows: "Any successful man should consult his wife, that is, every capable man should have a woman behind him." I was lucky to have someone like me who was frugal and hardworking. He was eager to help me in my work (It was lucky for me I had one as much disposed to industry and frugality as myself. She assisted me cheerfully in my business)" [5, p. 50]. By isolating himself from negative habits, Franklin was consciously trying to establish personal norms of behavior. He made great strides in following the rules of moral conduct and hoped that his successors would benefit from them (I hope, therefore, that some of my descendants may follow the example and reap the benefit) [4, p.57]. What made Franklin deal with self-upbringing? Why did he give priority to moral education when compiling rules of etiquette? Franklin gives a very clear answer to these questions in his autobiography. He writes: "As a child, I loved reading. My father's small library consisted mainly of polemical books on theology, many of which I read. Plutarch's book on the lives of prominent Greek and Roman statesmen and commanders was among them, and I read it a lot, and I still think I had a very productive time." (From my infancy I was passionately fond of reading ... My medicine little library consisted chiefly of books in polemic divinity, most of which I read ... There was among them Plutarch's Lives, in which I read abundantly, and I still think that time spent to great advantage) [5, p.35].

As can be seen, B. Franklin's reference to prominent personalities has a special place in his life. As it is known, in scientific pedagogy, the development of personality with reference to the positive aspects of the

lives of prominent personalities is considered one of the pedagogical rules. From the pages of B. Franklin's life and activity, he wanted to be like prominent people and leaders in his childhood, adolescence and youth, and as a result of his many studies and rich education, he became a prominent figure. So, American sources also contain valuable ideas and useful facts for a person-centered approach and citizenship upbringing.

There is a lot of information in the American written literature about the personal activities of the former President of the United States F. Roosevelt and his unique American citizenship. That information describes how F. Roosevelt became seriously ill and went to bed after earning a high academic degree. Roosevelt, who suffers from cerebral palsy, is unable to move. Unable to stand or move, F. Roosevelt does not stop reading while in bed. He does not tolerate the severity of his paralysis. Demonstrating a high will, F. Roosevelt began to write scientific works and scientific articles in bed. His series of works, which serve the formation of the country's economy, are very effective in organizing economic reforms in the country. His friends, who regularly visit him to check on the patient, ask him to develop his own platform and run for president. While struggling with a serious illness, F. Roosevelt does not stop writing works that benefit the country's economy. Roosevelt accepted the proposal of his friends and ran for the presidency. It should not be forgotten that in scientific pedagogy, self-motivation, self-demand, self-upbringing, self-education are presented as methods of personality-oriented approach and personality formation. There is an urgent need to use these examples, which are based on universal values, in educational work, especially in the process of civic education. That is why, with reference to international experience, we have included in the subsection a number of scientifically-pedagogical, methodologically substantiated views on the possibilities of personal development of civic education. John Locke was one of the English educators who developed a systematic theory of personality development. According to John Locke, nine out

of ten people become good or bad, useful or useless as a result of education. This means that if the upbringing, which is based in the family and continues regularly in school, is effective and beneficial, the educator can become a leader by his own behavior. Otherwise, if the upbringing in the family is not well organized, if the children are left unsupervised, if their bad deeds, faults, flaws and shortcomings are ignored, the future of those children will certainly result in unpleasant facts. They are isolated from society, imprisoned, and spend their lives in prisons. Of course, such an appreciation of John Locke's approach requires a productive approach to education in all ages. The purpose of education and the tasks arising from the goal is to train a gentleman who is able to carry out his work wisely and planned. Here we do not use the word gentleman by chance. A true gentleman must be a person who is physically, mentally and spiritually perfect. "As is the upbringing of man, so is he," wrote Locke. His pedagogical system played an important role in the development of the principles of education of a comprehensively developed personality. The main task of upbringing is to cultivate character, to cultivate a strong-willed person, to bring up a morally disciplined person. According to Locke, in order for parenting to work well, a child's individual qualities must be taken into account.

References

1. Babayev Javid Sabir. The values as a content in person-oriented education. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*. Vol. 3, Issue 5, 2023.
2. Goncharov N.K. *Basic pedagogy*. Moscow: Uchpedqiz, 1947
3. Pashayev AH, Rustamov FA, "Pedagogy", Baku, Chashyoglu, 2002, 512.
4. Seyidov A.Y. *History of pedagogy*. Baku, Maarif, 1968.
4. *The American Age of Reason*. Moscow, Progress publishers, 1964